

Art vs. Product

Goranka Stanić¹, Sandra Bačić², Branka Kožuh³

¹*Professor Advisor, Graduate engineer, School of Art and Design, Croatia, goranka.stanic@skole.hr*

²*Professor Advisor, Graduate engineer, School of Art and Design, Croatia
sandra.bacic2@ss-primijenjenaumjetnostidizajn-zd.skole.hr*

³*Professor Advisor, Graduate engineer, School of Art and Design, Croatia, kozuhbranka@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT: We are witnessing the development and opening of an increasing number of art schools and colleges. The curriculum covered by these organizations is versatile and comprehensive encompassing various emerging branches. However, a fundamental question arises: can inspired works of art be created when they are dictated by market demands and order, and to what extent mediocrity and kitsch are involved in such a process? Commercialism, pop, and marketing are susceptible areas when we talk about creation. The pandemic and the lockdown provided a unique opportunity to think, envision the future, and express our ideas. Art in the field of the market is looking for its place. Education needs to be directed and distracted from the automatic repetition of facts by increasing the level of "general culture" and encouraging pupils and students to focus on problem-solving so that they can use all available materials and resources. This kind of education enables the development of innovation rather than the complete repetition of facts. Nowadays, various media platforms and libraries inundate society with ideas and information. Progressing personally and contributing to society requires hard work. History represents the past, while homology teaches us how to upgrade and shape knowledge, but if we get stuck learning, we risk perpetuating old patterns through imitation. Therefore, it is crucial to look ahead, address problems and facilitate the enrichment of humanity's collective experience while upholding ethical principles and moral imperatives. This article emphasizes that art has a special place in this dynamic world.

KEYWORDS: art, product, marketing, education, innovation, creativity

1. Introduction

The time in which we live is full of information, the development of technologies, and industrial production. However, unfortunately, people equate their life, role, and value with material possessions, earnings, and money. Many works of art have no monetary value because these tools cannot measure the trends of inspiration and cognition. History has left us in various directions in art, the development of human consciousness, and the understanding of society, man, and his experiences more complex than mere photographic replication of the environment. Numerous art schools and academies are opening, and art seeks to connect with all aspects of human life. Multiple artistic directions are emerging: self-proclaimed, unaccepted, and commercial art. After schooling, individuals cautiously approach the name "being an artist, " despite their training and knowledge." At the same time, the multitude of people who create or instead form something -call themselves "self-proclaimed" artists. Art is impossible to define. Books are written and analyzed, sorted into various styles and branches, but the border is thin. In the category of artists, someone tries to put charlatans, kitsch, commercialism, and cheap creation for the masses. There are also some industrial branches of art, such as the film industry, applied arts, and graphic design.

Questionable is whether life, living, and nature can consider the most sublime art and whether man's creation merely imitates the creator. In calling for art's importance, it associates with all branches of activity, from science, technology, industry, upbringing, and education.

The analysis is whether today's art is the art of earning or expression. The artist is motivated to create an intriguing need to send a message or a vision or to sell and execute an order to the client within a specific price.

2. Art

2.1. Etymology of art

"Art" refers to the Latin word "ars," meaning art, skill, or craft. The first known use of the word art comes from a 13th-century manuscript. Nevertheless, the word art and its numerous variants (Artem, Ars.) have existed since the founding of Rome. Etymologically, the word art comes from the Latin ars, artist, and the Greek τέχνη (téchne), meaning "technique." In antiquity, art called for occupations such as blacksmithing and disciplines such as poetry, painting, or music (Encyclopedia - Struna 2004, 348)

2.2. Definition of Art

"Art is a set of disciplines or production of a human being for aesthetic and symbolic purposes based on a particular set of criteria, rules, and techniques." (Hrvatska Enciklopedija 2014, 247). Art is genuinely multiple categories, unknown as the soul itself. For real creators, art is much more significant and global than work. For them, it is the true meaning of life. Art seeks to present, in different ways, the universe of human concerns, whether real or imagined, using symbols or allegories. Art is the totality of human spiritual activity through how aesthetic experience is expressed, including the creation, the created work, and the experience of the work. Like art, there is a tendency to translate a work into objective existence by shaping feelings or ideas along with subsequent actions in the context of the work. The source of art is the cognition of an idea within which the subject is free from its individuality. Issue disappears in the object of art. Its message reveals that art is a uniquely human activity whose meaning constitutes a complex communication process between the artist, the work of art, and the audience. People have questioned art in different historical periods, but since the beginning of the modern era, we tend to attribute the following characteristics: Each work of art has its own highly developed and autonomous language; Art has an independent and free position in society; Art has no socially prescribed purpose; The purpose of art lies in fulfilling its contemporary defined nature, determined by the ideas of freedom, imagination, individuality, discovery, experiment, rebellion, beauty, truth, justice (mainly the ideas on which Western society is based in most of its segments such as the French Revolution.)The world, in modern society, does not only do what we see, hear, read, and touch but what we perceive as an art object. The "invisible" world of knowledge is about art, history, language, and rapid and current movements. We meditate on numerous cultural institutions (museums, galleries, libraries, publishers, art critics, concert halls, opera houses, art theory, and aesthetics.). Art is a curious kind of human activity. Consciousness can create - bringing into our material world what never existed. Art is often associated with creativity, but creativity is still a less significant category than art. Many artists paint; they are creative, but only some authors' work will be a generally recognized art or a cultural heritage. Creativity, together with art, satisfies the most critical spiritual needs of a person in self-expression. Art is a game of images created from imagination, which we manage to realize in real life.

2.3. Philosophy of art

Different artistic forms and periods are the subjects of systematic interpretations of aesthetics or aesthetic-philosophical theses of individual authors. The question of what art is has been debated among philosophers for centuries: "What is art?"

The most fundamental question in the philosophy of aesthetics is, "How will we determine what defines art?" This opinion implies two subtexts: the essential nature of art and its social significance (or lack thereof). Art can only be defined to meet one's criteria. A good explanation found in Webster's Ninth New College Dictionary says that art is "the conscious use of skill and creative imagination, especially (apparently) in the production of aesthetic objects." Based on this, the artist needs skill and creative imagination. When he puts these two abilities to work, he can create something that others find satisfying or attractive.

Immanuel Kant (1991, 198) was one of the most influential early theorists of the late 18th century. He considered it formalism in the sense of his philosophy. This meant that he believed that art should not have a concept but that it should be treated independently of formal properties and that the content of the work of art is not of aesthetic interest. On the other hand, science deals with acquiring and distributing human knowledge, and a rational approach to reality is crucial" (Kant 1991, 203).

Art is a unique form of cognition created by intuition. Intuition is the ability to predict, that is, the understanding that occurs before thinking and intellectual (logical) consciousness. Intuition is the knowledge used by imagination, not by the intellect, which is usually considered the creator of understanding.

It is always known individually and never in general. Intuition creates an image, while intellect creates a concept. It follows that art is cognition by instinct instead of science or philosophy in which consciousness is realized by reason." Understanding, which contained misunderstanding."

For the mathematical measurement of works of art, the instrumentation of geometry shows the basic format of the theorist. Such an interpretation of the work of art inspired Schopenhauer's advice to approach the painting like a king, waiting for the first to speak to us.

2.4. Quotes

There are as many ways to define art as there are people in the universe, and each definition affects that person's unique perspective, personality, and character. The following are a few sources that illustrate this range.

"Art evokes a secret without which the world would not exist." – Rene Magritte.

"Art is the discovery and development of the elementary principles of nature in beautiful forms suitable for human use." – Frank Lloyd Wright.

"Art allows us to find and get lost simultaneously." – Thomas Merton

"The purpose of art is to wash the dust of everyday life from our souls." – Pablo Picasso

"All art is only an imitation of nature." – Lucius Annaeus Seneca

"Art is not what you see but what you convince others." – Edgar Degas

"Art is the signature of civilizations." – Jean Sibelius

"Art is a human activity which consists in the fact that one man is conscious, using some external signs, gives to other feelings through which he has lived and that others are infected by these feelings and experience them" – Leo Nikolayevich Tolstoy

"Art is the making of ideas. Passion, violent or not, must never be expressed to cross the line of taste. And music, even when we are in the most terrible trouble, must never hurt our ears, but should flatter and seduce us". – Wolfgang Amadeus Mozart

"An artist is a hand that purposefully brings the human soul into vibration through this or that key." – Vasily Kandinsky

"An artist is nothing without talent, and talent is nothing without work." – Emile Zola

"Poets are interpreters of incomprehensible inspirations." – Percy Bysshe Shelley

"The whole world is a stage, and all men and women are just actors. They come on stage and off the stage, and during their lifetime, one human played many times." – Antun Gustav Matoš

"The artist belongs to his work, not the artist's work." – Georg Freiherr von Hardenberg

"The freedom to create depends on how obsessed you are with success." – Larry David

"We look at the past through the veil of art, and art, fortunately, still understands how to disguise reality." – Oscar Wilde

"Art lives within the obstacles it sets for itself and dies within others." – Albert Camus

"Real art is first and foremost the one that moves a kind of emotional wire in us, the one that upsets us in the most intimate feelings" – Ingmar Bergman

"Science and art are closely connected, like the heart and the lungs, and if one is damaged, the other cannot function properly." – Leo Nikolayevich Tolstoy

"Every work of art is a child of its time, and often, it is also the mother of our feelings." – Vasily Kandinsky

"Painting can be better shown on a palette than expressed in words." – Vincent van Gogh

"Artists who seek perfection in everything cannot achieve it in anything." – Eugene Delacroix

"Art is more valuable than truth." – Dionysius

"By changing people, the music changes the world." – Bono Vox

"Finding a form to describe the mess is the artist's job." – Samuel Beckett

"It is not painted with colors but with feelings." – Jean-Baptist Chardin

"For a work of art to be completely innovative, it must be written or painted in a complete paradox, and it cannot exist because otherwise, the artist would have to suffer from amnesia." – Manuel Frias Martins

"It is the artist's job to create, not to speak." – Johann Wolfgang von Goethe

"Art is not useful, but it is necessary." – La Corbusier

"It is up to art to create beautiful things, and it is up to a businessman to make economists." – Elbert Hubbard

"A great artist never sees things as they are." – Oscar Wilde

"Nothing that isn't practical can be beautiful." – Otto Wagner

"A man who writes well does not register as he writes, but he writes." – Louis de Montesquieu

"Art is always independent of life, and its color never reflects the color of the flag over the city fortress." – Viktor Shklovsky

"In art, it is like this: whoever is on the right path, no bad criticism can turn him off the right direction, and whoever is on the wrong way, no good criticism can lead him on the right path." – Matko Peić

"All the actor owns is his heart. It is a place where inspiration sough." – Meryl Streep

3. Product

3.1. Product definition

A product is the material result of production - everything we can offer someone to satisfy their need or desire (Hrvatska Enciklopedija 2014, 677). A total product - a set of tangible and intangible attributes that meet a consumer's need—can be a physical product, service, or a combination thereof, the result of human work in the material or spiritual creation made with the intention and plan. The product can be classified into three groups satisfying practical, spiritual, or aesthetic needs:

- Consumables - consumed in one or more uses
- Durable goods - that withstand repeated use
- Services - activities offered for sale.

When we use the term product, we come across various definitions. A product is a thing or object manufactured or invented of a material made by a natural or industrial process for the consumption or utility of individuals. A product is a generic term by which we can mean goods and services. A product is everything a company offers to consumers to meet their needs: a product resulting from a production activity that materializes in the economy. (Encyclopedia - Struna 2022, 675) Regardless of that activity, goods after manufacturing acquire an independent existence in their subject form. With its functional properties, it can satisfy a specific types of human needs. Each product results from a unique production

process and characterizes by special technology: the process it obtains and the kind of material it makes.

Products are all those objects or artifacts produced in industries, companies that follow the production line, or people's artistic way. Products can vary according to the proper life cycle. Some products have extended use, such as computers, books, or vehicles, but some products ship quickly, such as food, personal items, and medications.

Service is also a product, but not a material one, such as, for example, an internet connection, access to TV channels, hotel services, or social security, among others. Products are distinguished to be tangible or intangible.

Product means a consequence, effect, or result of a specific situation, circumstance, or action given to people. The durability of a product varies depending on its quality.

3.2. *Craft and art*

From the Renaissance onwards, there was a separation between arts and crafts in classic art. The difference between the two is that works of art are usually unique works attributed to the author's genius. On the other hand, the craft responds to the repetition of the traditional model, either by manual or industrial processes, because it is serial in each case.

Today, aesthetic sensibility is secondary and meaningless in most of society. The present is such that before a work of art, a worldly man, restrained by his blindness, will not notice the beauty expressed in the work, nor the message contained in it, but its market value or the name and reputation of the author.

A well-known anecdote about Picasso said in front of a picture of a beginner: "This picture lacks something else to be good." "What, master, what does it lack?" The beginner asked. "My signature is missing to be a great work of art," Picasso replied. However, the artist is not a signature. A work of art in itself should be able to touch a person. It needs to have its own life to separate itself from its creator. (Goodman 2002, 58).

The work of art was not born for its author's glory, but the artist's prize consisted of his transformation through artistic creation. It transcended the artist because he embodied something that was outside of him. He could glimpse it and give shape to it in the sensory world.

There is no universal definition of art, but there is a consensus that art is the conscious creation of something beautiful or meaningful using skill and imagination. Art is subjective, and the definition of art has changed throughout history and in different cultures. Jean Basquiat's Painting, which sold for \$ 110.5 million at Sotheby's auction in May 2017, would undoubtedly need help finding an audience in Renaissance Italy. Formal quality became particularly important as art became more abstract in the 20th century. The principles of art and design — balance, rhythm, harmony, and unity — were used to define and evaluate art.

Over the centuries in Western culture, from the 11th century until the end of the 17th century, art was anything done with skill as a result of knowledge and practice. Artists learned their craft, learning to replicate their subjects skillfully. The performance occurred during the Dutch Golden Age when artists could paint in various genres and make a living from their art in the robust economic and cultural atmosphere of the 17th-century Netherlands.

During the Romantic period of the 18th century, as a reaction to enlightenment and its emphasis on science, empirical proof, and rational thought, art began to be described as something done with skill and created in search of beauty and expressed artistic feelings. Nature glorifies, and spirituality and free expression celebrate. Artists themselves achieved a level of fame and were often guests of the aristocracy (Jašarević 2016, 141).

On the other hand, generating new ideas is also an art that only gets to some. Now creative ideas cost a lot of money and can bring popularity. Furthermore, if the idea is excellent, there will always be people who can implement it effectively. In the beginning, there were several types of art: painting, sculpture, architecture, fiction, singing, dancing,

music, and theater, but now there are many more. Photography, cinema, modeling, the advertising industry, show business, parkour - all this and much more- can be called modern art. Art reflects the mood that prevails in society, tastes, and habits.(Oršolić 2006, 204) That is why watching how creativity trends change over time is always interesting.

4. Market

4.1 Art as a Product

Art is the opposite of production. The product has more standards with research and development. When art becomes a manufactured product, it becomes a craft. It is the premise of this paper. Part of the creative industry creates an art product or, in some way, art. The question is how much we want to make art industrial and how much we want to make an art factory. Today there is almost no difference between a factory of works of art, a factory of shoes, a factory of dresses, or a factory of wall paintings, and between an artistic project and artistic things created here from art, from actual art.

Treating culture and art as a product has led to a distorted understanding of the purpose of public funds invested in culture and misunderstandings about the purpose of that investment. Culture becomes an investment that must pay off, affecting how culture manages (Rocco 2017, 87). There need to be criteria for evaluating culture and the quality of cultural events. They cannot be quantitative and only reflect the number of tickets sold or programs produced. In the art of a product, value is in the result, not in its production experience.

Product-oriented art does not stimulate playful creativity. Instead, art products are structured and focused activities that aim to produce a specific outcome. Art is a process or product of intentionally assembling elements to attract the senses or emotions. Art encompasses various human activities, creations, and methods of expression, including music, literature, film, sculpture, and painting. When we have a product, we use specialized knowledge and skills.

When the art industry comes on the market, there is only one type of relationship with a non-artist. A relationship with people is just a relationship between selling and buying (Infini Grupa 2023). Products are not based on selling and buying a ticket but on the fact that the artist and the people are all together and creating something in between. Such a relationship makes things complicated. We are still determining if we want to go this industrial route.

An original work of art is certainly not a service, like a plumber or a roofer, but it is free to work. The artist wants to avoid creating goods like manufactured goods (Huzjak 2011, 86-97). Although the artist does not think about his works using the word product, the result is for sale. Therefore the work of art is a product. Ultimately, the work wants to bring into other people's hands; Handmade pieces they sell by producing a product. Most people who consider themselves artists like to think that their work has some "higher goal." However, it is a product if trying to sell it (Dubrovnik Festival 2023). People place art in the world of representation in the context of the advertising industry.

4.2. The Price of ART

Deutsche Bank's collection includes over 50,000 works of art exhibited in the bank's offices and foyers. Among them are originals that many collectors would like to have in their collections. Deutsche Bank was among the first companies to exhibit works of contemporary art in the workplace as early as 1979 (Lambeck, 2008).

The results of contemporary art are displayed in the offices and hallways of the bank's buildings to help employees face aesthetic issues. This collection has been celebrated since it was exhibited in 1984 in the twin skyscrapers of that bank in Frankfurt. Then each floor was named after one artist or artist.

5. Analysis

Different views and understandings of art explain that real art is not a product. The work of art is of inestimable value, and by giving it the price of sale, we classify it in the category of goods for sale. Everything sold belongs to the variety of economy, marketing, and work is understood as a product or service. Today, many academic painters work to order. Such negotiations constrain the contractor's work, often with limited freedom, as clients determine the format, color, and theme and negotiate the price. Instead, many artists became employers, earning money through tickets, various shows, or the sale of works.

The high, intriguing, inspiring need to create and describe the experiences of the outer or inner world, visions, and messages cannot be ordered. In the way explained, the best, deeply intense, unlimited free works are created during inspiration, just what art should be.

6. Conclusion

The history of human existence in specific periods is characterized by art adapted to the social order and time. The famous handprint of the prehistoric person is the first scene of leaving a trace, a message. Throughout all stylistic periods, art is defined in an adapted way. While many musicians, painters, and other authors worked under the patronage of rulers, their works are now recognized as representative of the art of their respective periods. Whether the author's signature can increase the work's artistic value is questionable. Economics, marketing, and the market can set a price for any product, including artwork. If creativity is purely commercially motivated, it is classified as a sales value, that is—a product. Every work should be approached critically.

Real art is beyond monetary value. It is a part of someone's life and the world and was not created to please the audience but rather to spread the creator's message about the spirit of the times, problems, provocation, and injustice. The true purpose of art transcends its monetary value, resonating with the deeper essence of humanity.

References

- Dubrovnik Festival. 2023. *Tretiranje kulture i umjetnosti kao proizvoda?! (Treating culture and art as products?!)* Accessed on 07.02.2023. <https://www.dubrovnik-festival.hr/hr/novosti/%E2%80%99Etreiranje-kulture-i-umjetnosti-kao-proizvoda%E2%80%9C>.
- Encyclopedia - Struna 2004, 348, 675.
- Encyclopedia - Hrvatska Enciklopedija, Leksikografski zavod Miroslav Krleža, 2014, 247, 677.
- Goodman, N. 2002. *Jezici umjetnosti (Languages of art)*. Zagreb: KruZak.
- Huzjak, M. 2011. *Osjećaji, razum i umjetničko djelo (Feelings, reason and the work of art)*. Učiteljski fakultet, Sveučilište u Zagrebu. Zagreb.
- Infini Grupa. 2023. *Vrste inovacija – proizvod, proces, organizacija, marketing (Types of innovation – product, process, organization, marketing)*. Accessed on 07.02.2023. <https://infini.hr/vrste-inovacija-proizvod-proces-organizacija-marketing/>.
- Jašarević, M. 2016. *Između Apologije I Tjeskobe Tragičnog – Umjetnost Kao (Ne) Mirenje Sa Svijetom Kvantiteta I Brzine (Between Apology and Tragic Anxiety)*. Dzemal Bijedic University of Mostar.
- Kant, E. 1991. *Kritika moći suđenja*, Izdavačko-grafički zavod, Beograd. 15. Kundera.
- Lambeck, P. 2008. *Zbirka Deutsche Bank - umjetnost kao kapital (Deutsche Bank Collection - Art as Capital)*. Accessed on 07.02.2023. <https://www.dw.com/hr/zbirka-deutsche-bank-umjetnost-kao-kapital/a-3323793>.
- Oršolić, M. 2006. *Gdje smo? Tko smo? Kamo idemo? - umjetnost 20. Stoljeća (Where are we? Who are we? Where are we going? - art of the 20th century)*. University of Pula/Sveučilište Jurja Dobrile u Puli. <https://repozitorij.unipu.hr/islandora/object/unipu%3A404/datastream/PDF/view>.
- Rocco, S. 2017. *Upravljanje proizvodom, kreiranje marke i dizajn (Product management, brand creation and design)*, Visoka poslovna škola Zagreb.